

Heterocyclic-azo-dyes as Visual Indicators in the Titration of Ferrocyanide with Zinc

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Suitability of some heterocyclic azo dyes viz. AHP-4S, DHP-4S and CPD-4S has been examined in the titration of ferrocyanide with zinc. Colour change at the end point is orange to magenta. The studies have been made at room temperature. Interference due to diverse ions have been studied in detail. Statistical evaluations of each titrations have also been carried out.

ON addition of ferrocyanide ion to zinc(II) solution, a white precipitate of $Zn_2Fe(CN)_6$ is formed, which is converted by excess of the reagent into less soluble¹ $K_2Zn_3[Fe(CN)_6]_2$.

The traditional procedure for the determination of end point of the reactions utilizes uranyl nitrate and ammonium molybdate as external indicators. Numerous internal indicators such as diphenylamine, diphenylbenzidine, diphenylbenzidine sulphionate, *o*-dianisidine, naphthidine, 3,3'-dimethylnaphthidine, *p*-ethoxychrysoidine have been proposed as redox indicators²; quinine sulphate³ and 8-quinol-5-sulphonic acid⁴ as a fluorescence indicators; dithiozone in carbon tetrachloride and ferric ion as colour indicators and methyl red as an adsorption indicator have also been used.

In the present communication three different heterocyclic-azo-dyes have been used successfully as visual indicators for the titrimetric determination of ferrocyanide using zinc (II) sulphate as the titrant. These reagents have already been utilized for the complexometric determination of zinc(II), cadmium(II), mercury(II)⁴ and copper(II), cobalt(II), nickel (II)⁵. The formation of these dyes has been made use in determination of nitrite⁶.

Experimental

Reagents :

Standard Zinc(II) Sulphate Solution was prepared by dissolving requisite amount of zinc sulphate heptahydrate (B.D.H., A.R.) in doubly distilled water followed by addition of few drops of dilute sulphuric acid and standardized complexometrically using ELTA as titrant and Eriochrome Black T as indicator.

Standard Potassium Ferrocyanide Solution was prepared by dissolving appropriate amount of potassium ferrocyanide (B.D.H., A.R.) in doubly distilled water.

Dye Solution : 0.25% (w/v) solutions of the dyes in doubly distilled water were used throughout the study. The dyes were isolated by diazotizing sulphanilic acid and subsequently coupling the resulting diazotized product with three different substituted hydroxypyridines viz., 2-amino-3-hydroxypyridine (AHP), 2,3-dihydroxypyridine (DHP) and 5-chloropyridine-2, 3-diol (CPD). On the basis of elemental analysis and colour reactions which they give with metal ions, following tentative structures have been assigned to the dyes.

- (I) 1-(2-amino-3-hydroxy-4-pyridylazo)-benzene-4-sulphonic acid (AHP-4S)
(II) 1-(2,3-dihydroxy-4-pyridylazo)-benzene-4-sulphonic acid (DHP-4S)
(III) 1-(5-chloro-4-pyridylazo-2, 3-diol)-benzene-4-sulphonic acid (CPD-4S)

Recommended Procedure :

To a suitable aliquot containing 0.2-10.6 mg of ferrocyanide ion, add 5 ml of pyridine buffer of pH 8.0 and 0.1-0.3 ml of 0.25% indicator solution (AHP-4S, DHP-4S or CPD-4S). Dilute the solution approximately to 20 ml by adding doubly distilled water and titrate at room temperature (27°) with shaking against standard zinc(II) sulphate solution ($1 \times 10^{-2} M$) taken in a micro burette till a sharp colour change (orange to magenta) is obtained. Titrations in reverse order can also be performed with equal accuracy and ease.

For accurate results, the amount of ferrocyanide should be taken between 0.2-10.6 mg.

Titration in the presence of diverse ions :

To explore the possibility of performing these titrations in the presence of various interfering ions (anions and cations), titrations were performed by taking 4.24 mg of ferrocyanide and adding foreign ions in varying proportions and following the recommended procedure as given above. Masking agents were also used to undo some of the interferences of the cations Table 1.)

TABLE—1 INTERFERENCE OF DIVERSE IONS

Interfering ions	With AHP-4S, PPM	With DHP-4S, PPM	With CPD-4S, PPM	Masking Agent, if any
F ⁻ , Cl ⁻ , Br ⁻ , I ⁻	5,000	5,000	5,000	-
NO ₂ ⁻ , NO ₃ ⁻	5,000	5,000	5,000	-
SO ₄ ⁻² , SO ₃ ⁻²	5,000	5,000	5,000	-
Acetate	5,000	5,000	5,000	-
ClO ₄ ⁻	5,000	5,000	5,000	-
Citrate, Tartrate	5,000	5,000	5,000	-
Thiourea	5,000	5,000	5,000	-
C ₂ O ₄ ⁻²	5,000	500	100	-
S ₂ O ₃ ⁻²	500	500	500	-
BO ₃ ⁻³	Interferes	500	500	-
CNS ⁻	300	300	100	-
S ₂ O ₈ ⁻²	5,000	2,000	1,000	-
Ti(IV)	240	240	240	-
Sb(III)	609	1,218	609	-
Pd*(II)	32	10	10	I'
W(VI)	5,000	5,000	5,000	-
Ge(IV)	100	100	100	-
V(V)	51	31	5	-
Sr(II)	5,000	5,000	5,000	-
Pb(II)*	21	8	21	I'
Sn(II)*	50	50	50	F'
Ti(I)	5,000	5,000	5,000	-
In(III)	230	12	23	-
Hg(II)*	10	50	100	I'
Ru(III)	20	20	20	-
Cd(II)*	2.2	2.2	2.2	I'
Mn(II)	5.5	5.5	2.8	-
Fe(II)	11	5	Interferes	-
Ir(III)	10	10	10	-
La(III)	28	28	14	-
Pr(III)	14	14	14	-
Y(III)	71	18	18	-
Yb(III)	35	17	17	-
Rh(III)	25	25	30	-
Ag(I)*	1,000	1,000	1,000	I'
Al(III)*	51	34	34	F'

*Metal ions masked with anions indicated in the last column. However, PO₄⁻³, S⁻², CN⁻, Cu(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Os(VIII) and Ce(III) interferes very seriously even in traces.

To check the precision and accuracy of the methods six identical solutions of ferrocyanide were titrated against zinc(II) solution using each of the above indicators. Statistical evaluation of the results are summarised in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

The various factors such as effect of indicator concentration, concentration of the metal ion, pH and temperature were investigated and optimum conditions for accurate titration of ferrocyanide with zinc(II) solutions using AHP-4S, DHP-4S and CPD-4S have been established. Attempts have also been made to determine ferrocyanide in the presence of large number of diverse ions, through masking etc. (Table 1). Statistical evaluation of the results were also carried out on the basis of six titrations under identical conditions (Table 2).

J. C. Bailor et al.¹ have assumed the ferrocyanide : zinc ratio either 1 : 2 or 2 : 3 corresponding to the species Zn₂Fe(CN)₆ or K₂Zn₃[Fe(CN)₆]₂. In our case, the ferrocyanide : zinc ratio is 1 : 2, which corresponds to the species Zn₂Fe(CN)₆, a white precipitate sparingly soluble in water.

Titrimetric determination of ferrocyanide using AHP-4S, DHP-4S and CPD-4S as visual indicators in pyridine buffer, with zinc(II) sulphate solution as titrant, is rapid and reliable. The colour changes at the end points are sharp and instantaneous. No indicator correction is required. All the titrations can be performed at room temperature (27°)

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TABLE—2 TITRATION OF FERROCYANIDE WITH ZINC(II) SULPHATE USING AHP-4S, DHP-4S AND CPD AS VISUAL INDICATORS

Indicator	Ferrocyanide taken in mg	Standard deviation	Variation coefficient	Relative width of confidence interval at 95% (α = 0.5)	Relative Error m%
AHP-4S	4.24	0.024	0.57	4.24 ± 0.025	0.42
DHP-4S	4.24	0.019	0.45	4.24 ± 0.020	0.33
CPD-4S	4.24	0.024	0.57	4.24 ± 0.025	0.42

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